

A Study on Impact of Work Stress on Entrepreneurs – “With Special Reference to Cottage Industries”

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INTRODUCTION

The new modernization world have been faced various kinds of problems especially business men Facing large level of problems through their work environment, around the world each and every day changes new technologies, new trend of life, new information etc. these factors creates heavy competitions among the business men, especially affects the new entrepreneurs, the new entrepreneurs having lots of dreams and expectations for their business field, however to-day business field creates high level of depression and stress , due to various unanticipated problems issues and challenges.

MEANING AND DEFINITION:

A person undergoes stress when he feels that he is ill-equipped to carry out the tasks assigned to him. Total absence of stress may affect performance. A person needs to undergo a certain level of stress to perform well, excessive stress is harmful,

Stress arises when a person is unable to meet the demands of the situation owing to his mental and /or physical in capacity.

“A state of psychological and physiological imbalance resulting from the disparity between situation demand and the individual’s ability and motivation to meet those needs” - Gaurav akrani

“The rate of all wear and tear caused by life”

- Hans Selye

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

To-days modernization world businessmen especially new entrepreneurs getting high-level of stress, it

creates mind depression, BP, mind affect, life style affect, even for suicide etc. so how to relive these problems and stress free entrepreneurs in the world.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE:

1. J.JAYASANKAR. (2006) explains the problems of stress is not peculiar to a formal work place like on office or a business establishment, even housewives undergo stress may be physical as well metal

2. CRYSTAL L.PARK et all. (1996) examining determinants of stress related positive outcomes for college students. Study 1 analyses showed that the SRGI has acceptable internal and test retest reliability and that scores are not influenced by social desirability, study 2 analyses showed that college students SRGS response were significantly related to those provided by friends and relatives on their behalf. Study analyses tested growth longitudinally. Significant predictors of the SRGS were (a) intrinsic religiousness; (b) social support satisfaction; (c) positive reinterpretation and acceptance coping; and (e) number of recent positive life events. The SRGS was also positively related to residual change in optimism, positive affectivity, number of socially supportive others, and social support satisfaction, lending further support to the validity of the new scale. Results have implications for current theory on stress related positive outcomes.

3. LAWRENCE.H COLEN et all (1998) Enumerates research with the SRGS suggests a unidimensional structure of thriving. Whereas research with the PTGI suggest a multidimensional

structure. Two possible reasons for this consistent findings concern differences in the method of participant selection in the recall period for the reporting of stressful events. In addition, we validate self – report measures of thriving; including corroboration from significant other and the use of the control groups. We conclude with a brief discussion of the assessment of thriving at the group and community levels.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To critically review the current position of stress in entrepreneurs.
2. To examine the role of stress in business field
3. To examine the sources of stress in entrepreneurs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The study is mainly based on secondary data. The secondary data have been collected in various journals, books, websites, periodicals, some leading newspapers etc.

PERIOD OF THE STUDY:

In order to make this research work to reflect the current status of stress and impact of stress in entrepreneurs, the period of study has been fixed at one year from **May-2016 to April-2017**

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

Any research work will have its own limitations. Therefore the present study is not an exceptional to this.

- This study is based on only secondary data.
- This study is focuses only cottage industries.
- The data mainly collected websites, journals, and books.
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ANALYSES AND INTERPRETATION OF THE DATA:

Stress in entrepreneur:

Entrepreneurs facing various types of stress and depression, the important only given in the following mannered.

Table No: 1:

TYPES OF STRESS AND DEPRESSION

SI no	TYPES OF STRESS AND DEPRESSION
1	Loneliness
2	Fear of the unknown
3	Financial problems
4	Work load
5	Amount of responsibility
6	Managing time and dead lines
7	Public speaking / pitching
8	Finding the right team
9	Customer interaction
10	Rest

Source: Secondary data

Stress on entrepreneurs in cottage industries:

Stress problem is omnipresent in every human being. It's also for Small and cottage business entrepreneurs, due to they are new to the business world, they facing lots of unexpected problems, therefore they gets high degree of stress in work field, the maximum stress creating field are

- Hand- loom weaving (Cotton, Silk, jute, etc.)
- Pottery
- Washing soap making
- Conch Shell industry
- Handmade Paper industry
- Horn button industry
- Mother of pearl button industry
- Cutlery industry
- Lock and key making industry

CAUSES OF STRESS

- Ability
- Perception
- Manner of approaching crises
- Level of self-confidence
- Experience
- Desire for work
- Beliefs

- Nature of job
- Superior subordinate relationships
- Inter personal relationships
- Target to be reached
- Time pressure
- Physical working conditions
- Opportunity for advancement& hours of work
- Disparity in pay in pay and other benefits
- Punitive measures like demotion, suspension etc

FINDINGS SUGGESTION:

- Most of the entrepreneurs getting stress through organizational factors
- Entrepreneurs also getting stress from personal factors
- Stress affects mind set of the entrepreneurs as well as production and service of the concern
- Stress creates uneven life style of the entrepreneurs
- Stress affects personal and social life.

- The employer can cope with stress by adopting any of the following measures
 - Understanding self
 - Doing work systematic and planned manner
 - Need routine physical exercise and yoga
 - Developing a positive attitude towards life and work
 - Maintaining healthy diet

SUGGESTION:

- Entrepreneurs needs the stress relief process through some prevention of the activities such as Create good work condition, better relationship with others, and unbiased activities of the employee etc
- The entrepreneurs can escape stress by some changes of activities such as providing free lunch, promotion for workers, creates good ventilations, and other employee welfare related activities etc.

CONCLUSION:

Now a days we are living complicated environment in the world, the life style changes each and every moment of the daily life, we are facing lots of problems and challenges in our life, its affects our mind set, these mind set affect also affects routine life style, these affect mainly in some critical work field especially business personality even for entrepreneurial activities. We need for stress free countries in the world for entrepreneurs, need for stress relief through physically and mentally, such as yoga, meditation, proper exercise, healthy diet, positive attitude towards life etc.

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